

The vulnerability of regional agriculture regarding irrigation water from the Tagus-Segura transfer

José Daniel Buendía Azorín ^{a,*},¹, Rubén Martínez Alpañez ^{b,2},
María del Mar Sánchez de la Vega ^{c,3}

^a Department of Applied Economics, University of Murcia, Campus de Espinardo S/N, Murcia 30100, Spain

^b Researcher at GALA Group "CSR, Sustainability, and Innovation" UCAM

^c Department of Quantitative Methods for Economy and Business, University of Murcia, Campus de Espinardo S/N, Murcia 30100, Spain

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ABSTRACT

Input–output tables provide a useful tool for analysing economic and environmental impacts, which has led to their extension beyond the national level to the regional level. The availability of the intermediate demand matrix allows for the extraction of income multipliers and employment multipliers to assess the environmental impacts of different economic activities. This can intuitively be expected to play an important role in economic growth and employment in many regions, and to allow for more precise policy decision-making and application in sustainable development strategies. Despite the relevance of these input-output tables at regional level, there is an almost total absence of official data in most countries. This has led to the development of regionalisation methodologies, among which are those based on the application of location quotients. In these methods, corrections are applied to the obtained variables that depend on the value given to certain unknown parameters. This paper uses a proposal of a simple and efficient procedure for estimating these parameters from generally available information on road freight transport and goods imports from the rest of the world. Applying them to estimate the input-output matrix of the Region of Murcia (Spain) made it possible to measure the economic impact of the Tagus-Segura transfer and to assess the impact of a reduction in the volume of transferable water. A hybrid approach was applied to obtain the Bi-Regional Input-Output matrix, which combines pure non-survey methods with matrix-balancing methods. This study quantifies the total contribution (direct, indirect and induced) of the agricultural branches associated with the irrigation water of the Tagus-Segura transfer to the economic output of the Region of Murcia. In addition, it estimates that a 50 % reduction of the current transferable volume of water would reduce regional output, Gross Value Added and regional employment by 1.6 %, 1.5 % and 3.8 %, respectively.

1. Introduction

In the field of river transfers, researchers have expressed concerns about the economic, social, and environmental impacts on the benefiting areas. However, the majority of studies have approached these impacts separately. On one hand, environmental assessments, for instance, have been conducted by various studies (e.g., Davies et al.,

1992; Meador, 1992; Gibbins, 2000; Ibáñez and Prat, 2003; Matete and Hassan, 2005; Das, 2006; Hu et al., 2008; Islar and Boda, 2014) using cause-effect interaction matrices. On the other hand, research on economic impacts, which is the focus of this study, has gained momentum since the seminal work of Howe and Easter (1971)⁴. This interest is evidenced by numerous publications, including those by Beattie (1972), Howe et al. (1990), Seung et al. (1998), Sánchez-Chóliz and Duarte

* Corresponding author.

E-mail addresses: jbuen@um.es (J.D.B. Azorín), ruben.ma@um.es (R.M. Alpañez), marvega@um.es (M.M. Sánchez de la Vega).

¹ ORCID: 0000-0001-9302-7971

² ORCID:0000-0002-3663-3171

³ ORCID: 0000-0002-8647-6215

⁴ This paper presents the conceptual framework for the economic evaluation and case study of the transfer of the Columbia River to the Imperial Valley of California in the United States, using the input-output framework.

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(2000), Gómez et al. (2004), Velázquez (2006), Tirado et al. (2006), Gao and Yu (2018), and Xu et al. (2023). These studies have evaluated economic impacts using models such as Input-Output (I-O)⁵ models or computational general equilibrium (CGE) models.

In this context, the present work extends the literature on economic impacts of transfers between rivers, using Input-Output analysis.

The Input-Output model not only allows for the evaluation of economic aspects but also facilitates the analysis of environmental and social dimensions. For instance, it can quantify the amount of CO₂ emitted per unit of food produced or assess the employment generated per unit of investment. In addition, other methodologies such as Life Cycle Assessment, Key Performance Indicators, and the Leopold Matrix have been employed to assess the environmental and social impacts of various projects.

Input-output tables are recognised as a useful tool for analysing economic impacts and structural analysis, which has led to their extension beyond the national level to the regional level. The economic structure of the Region of Murcia (Spain) differs completely from the national average and, considering the interconnections with the Rest of Spain, is relevant for its study.

Such is the case of the agricultural sector in the Region of Murcia, whose economic, social and environmental implications render it strategic. Hence, in terms of the economy, based on 2021 data, this sector represents 11.1% of total regional employment, 5.3% of regional GVA and 35.9% of regional exports while contributing to territorial structuring with significant forward (agri-food industry, marketing, hospitality, etc.) and backward (animal feed, plant protection products, fertilisers, seeds) effects on the regional economy as a whole. From a social and environmental point of view, agriculture is essential to ensure the supply of foodstuffs and the conservation of natural resources through the care and maintenance of soils, landscapes and biodiversity. This relevance is, however, highly dependent on the availability of irrigation water from the Tagus-Segura transfer.

There is currently a high degree of uncertainty as to how the effects of climate change may affect the achievement of environmental objectives in the Tagus basin as well as how they may affect the new regulation of ecological flows that are compatible with the current transferable volumes of the Tagus-Segura Aqueduct.

The Region of Murcia is part of the Segura basin, which also includes the autonomous communities of Andalusia, Castile-La Mancha and the Valencian Community. This geographical area of south-eastern Spain is characterised by a shortage of water, despite which agriculture, especially irrigated agriculture, is a key sector in the productive structure. This water deficit has also been exacerbated by demographic and tourist pressure, especially in coastal areas. According to Pulido et al. (2020), the geographical and climatic contrasts in Spain are manifested in a clear asymmetry between the northern area and the rest of the peninsular territory, both in the availability of water and in the favourable climatic conditions for agriculture in large areas in the south. This geographical and temporal imbalance between water availability (north) and demand (south) has been addressed by building water infrastructures, a process not without conflict, which has also led to significant institutional development: water courts, irrigation communities, hydrographic confederations, etc.

In this context, the aim of this paper is to present a case study of the Region of Murcia where the economic importance of the Tagus-Segura transfer is analysed using a Bi-Regional Input-Output matrix of the Region of Murcia (IOTRM) and the Rest of Spain regions (IOTROS). First, however, the regional Input-Output matrix had to be obtained, as it was not available. Among the most commonly used techniques for estimating or regionalising input-output tables are those based on Location Quotients (LQs), (Flegg et al., 1995; Flegg and Webber, 1997, 2000); the

two-dimensional location quotient, 2D-LQ, (Pereira-López et al., 2020, 2021), and an alternative to the pure LQ-based methods is the Demand and Supply based Location Quotient, DSLQ, (Fujimoto, 2019). To go through the estimation of the regional Input-Output matrix of the Region of Murcia, this work uses a hybrid non-survey approach which combines the recent DSLQ technique and, additionally, the matrix balancing methods like RAS and the Jahn methodology (2017). In order to estimate the parameter associated with the DSLQ, this work uses a simple and efficient proposal for that estimation based on information on freight transport by road and the regional size. Based on the afore-mentioned methodology, the input-output matrix is estimated for the Region of Murcia.

A significant amount of the irrigation water for the agricultural sector of the Region of Murcia comes from the Tagus-Segura Rivers transfer. The Water Management Plan of the Spanish side of the Tagus River Basin District, approved by Royal Decree 14/2016, establishes the minimum flows and ecological flows, ratified by up to five rulings of the Supreme Court. The implementation of these ecological flows foresees a 50% reduction in the water transferred from the Tagus to the Segura for irrigation purposes. Using the input-output table obtained, the economic impact of irrigation water from the transfer is estimated, as well as the impact of a possible 50% reduction in the amount of water transferred.

Therefore, this study offers two main contributions. The first one consists of proposing a simple and efficient method for estimating the parameters associated with the FLQ, 2D-LQ, and DSLQ. This approach relies on data concerning freight transport by road and imports from the rest of the world to construct an input-output framework for the Region of Murcia. The second contribution involves conducting a case study of economic impact analysis, focusing on the effects of irrigation water derived from the Tagus-Segura rivers transfer. This analysis is based on the regional input-output table obtained through the above methodology.

While there are no previous works directly comparable to the present study in the strict sense, several related contributions offer valuable insights. For instance, Alcalá and Sancho (2002) analyzed the relationship between irrigated agricultural production and water resource availability in the Region of Murcia for the period 1981–1997. Melgarejo and Martínez (2009) assessed the economic influence of the Tajo-Segura transfer on agriculture in Murcia, Alicante, and Almería by estimating crop production values in irrigable areas using indicators. Villar (2009) estimated the water price system for irrigation and carried out a supply-demand analysis of the Tajo-Segura irrigation systems. Additionally, PricewaterhouseCoopers (2013) employed the input-output method to estimate production value and employment in the agricultural sector of the Irrigable Zones of the Tajo-Segura Transfer.

In relation to this, it should be noted that the hybrid estimation method of the table input-output for the Region of Murcia used in this work represents a significant innovation in the field of non-survey techniques developed to date. This method provides an estimate of the regional input-output table with high accuracy compared to the real one (Buendía-Azorín et al., 2022). Furthermore, utilizing this estimation enhances the evaluation of the impact of the Tajo Segura transfer, as it allows for data on the productive structure that is more closely aligned with regional reality compared to previous works (Melgarejo and Martínez, 2009; PricewaterhouseCoopers, 2013). This aspect constitutes the main innovation compared to these works, which rely on the national input-output table, whose productive structure notably differs from that of the Region of Murcia, often leading to results with greater bias. Additionally, for the first time in this study, the direct, indirect, and induced impacts are estimated for each of the five branches of activity in the agricultural sector.

In summary, this work addresses the following issues:

- The significance of the Tagus-Segura water transfer for agriculture and the regional economy: This study hypothesizes that irrigation water from the Tagus-Segura transfer plays a critical role in

⁵ The input-output model is a particular case of general equilibrium models. For a comprehensive analysis see Cardenete et al. (2012).

supporting regional agricultural output, gross value added, and employment in Murcia. This hypothesis is tested by estimating the total economic contribution of the transfer to the region.

- The impact of a 50% reduction in transferable irrigation water on the regional economy: The hypothesis formulated is that a 50% reduction in the amount of transferable irrigation water, prompted by environmental regulations, would have a significantly negative impact on the region's production, GVA, and employment. This assumption is evaluated through the use of Input-Output (I-O) analysis to measure the potential economic consequences of such a reduction.

The methodology used to test these hypotheses is based on the applicability and effectiveness of the input-output methodology in quantifying economic and social impacts. An input-output (IO) model can provide clear, precise, and accurate measurements of the economic relevance of various activities, as well as the impacts of economic, social, or environmental shocks. Consequently, the analysis conducted in this study is based on the construction of a bi-regional IO matrix for the Region of Murcia.

A key aspect in constructing the IO matrix is the application of the DSLQ method, which includes an enhanced approach to estimating the associated parameters, developed by the authors. This approach offers superior accuracy in estimating regional economic impacts compared to other regionalization techniques based on location quotients.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Delimitation of irrigated agricultural activities of the Tagus-Segura transfer

In order to estimate the impact of the Tagus-Segura transfer on the generation of production, gross value added and employment in the Region of Murcia, the agricultural economic activities associated with irrigation and which are dependent on the water provided by the Tagus-Segura transfer must be precisely delimited. In the specific case in question, crop production⁶ has been grouped into the following branches of activity: [1] Cereals and other extensive crops; [2] Horticulture; [3] Fresh fruit; [4] Citrus; and [5] Viticulture, olive groves and other woody crops. The rest of the agricultural sector is [6] animal production. Based on the data on Production, Intermediate Consumption, Gross Value Added at basic prices and its components (compensation of employees, taxes and subsidies on production and gross operating surplus) of the agricultural sector published in the Farming Economic Accounts, these variables have been distributed among the different branches of agricultural activity according to the criterion of their relative weight, based on the disaggregated information of these variables in the Farm Type of the vegetable production published in the Farm Accountancy Data Network. Labour has been distributed among the different agricultural activities according to the relative weighting of compensation of employees in each branch of agricultural activity. The values of the relevant economic variables of these agricultural activities

⁶ According to Farm Type (FT) classification of crop production, the activities are grouped into the following categories: [15] Cereals, oilseeds and protein crops; [16] Other extensive annual crops; [20] Horticulture; [35] Viticulture; [36] Fruits; [37] Olive Groves; [38] Other woody crops. The rest of the agricultural sector consists mainly of animal production: [45] Dairy cattle; [48] Sheep, goats and other grazing livestock; [45] Cattle for breeding and meat; [50] Granivores and the categories [60], [70] and [80] Mixed agriculture and livestock.

such as GVA, compensation of employees, gross operating surplus, subsidies and taxes on production and labour were estimated using the publications of the agricultural statistics (National Farm Accountancy Data Network and Agricultural Economic Accounts) of the Spanish Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries and Food and the Social Security affiliation data of the Ministry of Labour and Social Economy for the year 2015.

Table 1 shows the economic relevance of the entire agricultural sector (crop production and livestock production), which is closely linked to favorable climatic conditions that enhance the productive yield of various crops. However, its true impact goes beyond the economic dimension, extending to the social and environmental realms, playing a significant role in international trade, territorial cohesion, and the conservation and maintenance of natural spaces. Quantitatively, the agricultural sector as a whole represents 4.6% of the output, 5.8% of the gross value added (GVA), and 10.9% of employment in the Region of Murcia, whereas at the national level, its participation is significantly lower at 2.2%, 3.0%, and 4.0%, respectively. Focusing specifically on the agricultural branches from [1] to [5] related to the Tagus-Segura transfer, the value of the production of the vegetable agricultural activities is €1,858 million in 2015, which represents 6.9% of the output value of these national branches. Among these agricultural branches associated with irrigation in the Tagus-Segura transfer, vegetables are predominant with a production value of €882 million (9.8% of Spain's production), fresh fruits with a value of €508 million (8.1% of the national total) and citrus fruits with a production value of €440 million (17.9% of Spain's total), figures that indicate that these activities are highly competitive and decisive for the generation of income and employment in the Region of Murcia. The GVA generated by these agricultural branches is estimated at €1,041 million (4.0% of the regional GVA), of which horticulture contributes €475 million (8.1% of the Spanish total), fresh fruits contribute €299 million (6.8% of the Spanish total) and citrus fruits generate €259 million (15.0% of the national total). In terms of employment, these agricultural activities support 65,595 jobs (12.8% of regional employment), with horticulture contributing 30,762 (6.0%); fresh fruits, 18,497 (3.6%); and citrus fruits, 16,079 (3.1%).

As the main purpose is to measure the contribution of the Tagus-Segura transfer to production and to income and employment generation in the Region of Murcia, an important and decisive step is to delimit the values of these macro-magnitudes directly linked to the use of water from the Tagus-Segura transfer. In order to establish the existing link between the agricultural activities that use water from the Tagus-Segura transfer and the relevance of this water input in the output of these activities, Table 2 shows the distribution of water consumption according to its typology (transfer, desalinated, wells and basin) and the surface area used according to the types of crops grouped into the different agricultural branches ([1] Cereals and other extensive crops; [2] Horticulture; [3] Fresh fruits; [4] Citrus and [5] Viticulture, olive groves and other woody crops) by Irrigation Zones of the aqueduct. Consumption was 147.14hm³, of which the majority, 96.88hm³, came from the aqueduct (65.8%). The irrigable areas that use most of the water from the transfer are those of Campo de Cartagena, which consumes 46.42hm³ (47.9% of the total) and Guadalentín Valley Sectors 7 and 8, which uses 10.40hm³ (10.7% of the total). In terms of cultivated surface area, the Campo de Cartagena area is also the most important with a total of 43,072 ha, representing 21.1% of the total surface area. The most important crops in this area are open-air horticultural crops (63.8%) and citrus fruits (29.9%).

On average, the volume of water used in the irrigable areas of the Tagus-Segura transfer was 751.3m³/ha/year, of which 494.6m³/ha/year corresponds to water from the transfer.

Table 1

Macro-magnitudes of agricultural activities at basic prices in 2015. *Source:* Authors' compilation based on data from the Spanish Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries and Food, National Farm Accountancy Data Network (FADN) and Farm Economic Accounts (FEA).

Variables	[1]	[2]	[3]	[4]	[5]	[6]	Total
Output (thousand €)	18,662	882,813	507,843	440,408	8,247	744,363	2,602,336
Intermediate consumption (thousand €)	12,864	405,884	208,079	180,379	3,215	486,571	1,296,992
Gross value added _{bp} (thousand €)	3,728	475,033	298,631	259,586	4,528	251,984	1,293,490
Compensation of employees (thousand €)	187	130,306	78,352	68,108	903	42,903	320,759
Net taxes on production (thousand €)	-2,155	-14,018	-15,511	-13,483	-620	-73,434	-119,221
Gross operating surplus (thousand €)	5,696	358,746	235,789	204,961	4,245	282,515	1,091,950
Employment (persons)	44	30,762	18,497	16,079	213	10,128	75,723

The irrigation production coefficients and use coefficient are estimated based on the information on the surface area dedicated to agricultural use⁷ of the Segura Hydrographic Demarcation (SHD) – in which the net irrigation surface area per unit of agricultural demand (ADU) is presented with the most representative crops of each one of them⁸ and that relating to the water consumption for irrigation of the irrigable areas of the Tagus-Segura transfer by type of crop. These coefficients allow the impact of irrigation water for agriculture from the Tagus-Segura transfer in the Region of Murcia to be measured more accurately. The irrigation production coefficient makes it possible to estimate the value of the production of the different agricultural crop branches that is linked to the irrigated area.⁹ The use coefficient¹⁰ measures the value of production generated by the agricultural crop branches as a function of the percentage of irrigation water use of the Tagus-Segura transfer in relation to the total water consumed by the different crop types (Table 3). In other words, it attempts to adjust the value of the production of the irrigated area according to the different water requirements (m³/ha) of each type of crop according to the proportion of irrigation water from the Tagus-Segura transfer in the different zones. Table 4 shows the values of the production and use coefficients.

By applying the production adjustment and use coefficients to the corresponding values of the agricultural production branches, the estimate of the adjusted value of the production, gross added value and employment that is generated directly by the irrigation water of the Tagus-Segura transfer are obtained (Table 5). Thus, the gross production generated directly by irrigation water from the transfer in the vegetable agricultural branches reaches the value of 1,076 million euros. The direct contribution of gross added value is estimated at 601 million euros and the employment requirement used reaches the figure of 38,100 people.

⁷ This area is grouped into agricultural demand units (ADU) which share common characteristics according to the fundamental criterion of constituting a differentiable management unit, either due to the origin of their resources, their administrative conditions, their irrigation technology, their hydrological similarity or strictly territorial considerations.

⁸ The surface area values for each crop were obtained from the percentages of surface area of each crop estimated for 2013 in the remote sensing work carried out by the Hydrographic Planning Office of the Hydrographic Confederation of the Segura River.

⁹ The estimate was made by applying the proportion of irrigated area (ha) to the total area (ha) of each productive branch. For this purpose, the area by type of crop and cropping system has been previously aggregated from the data published by the Regional Ministry of Agriculture, Livestock, Fisheries and Food of the Region of Murcia for 2015. <https://econet.carm.es/web/crem/iniio/-/crem/sicrem/PU590/sec0.html>.

¹⁰ To estimate this coefficient, the weighted average of the water requirement (m³/ha) is first determined for each agricultural branch in each zone and multiplied by the surface area of each zone and for each type of product. This gives the total water requirement for each agricultural branch and zone. The proportion of irrigation water from the Tagus-Segura transfer is then applied to these branch and zone requirements (Table 9). The ratio between these latter values and the total water requirements for each productive branch determines the use coefficient.

2.2. Regionalisation methodology of input-output tables: the use of location quotients

A hybrid methodology was used to estimate the Input Output Table for the Region of Murcia (IOTRM), combining statistical techniques to establish the structure of the IOTRM using the Input Output Table for Spain (IOTS) and information obtained from surveys on production sectors or consumption structures, available at regional level.

The first step in a regionalisation procedure is implemented using location quotients. This requires the use of input-output tables that differentiate between domestic sectoral interrelations, referring to the territory in question, covered by the IOT, and those established with the rest of the world via foreign trade of goods and services. This process may lead to an IOTRM in which domestic intersectoral flows are differentiated, relative to the Region of Murcia and those established both with the rest of Spain and with the rest of the world. Thus, it will be possible to calculate the regional impacts produced in the face of certain variations or shocks that are modulated to that effect.

In this work, both matrices (IOTRM and IOTROS) were constructed by means of indirect methods based on (LQs). The use of location quotients is an appropriate tool in cases where no regional input-output framework is available (Flegg et al., 1995).

Several studies highlight the suitability of this regionalisation methodology (Mastronardi and Romero, 2012; Lamonica and Chelli, 2018; Flegg et al., 1995; Flegg and Webber, 2000; Lampiris et al., 2019), which has been widely used for the estimation of regional or national tables, such as Argentina (Flegg et al., 2016; Mastronardi et al., 2022), Finland (Flegg and Tohmo, 2013), Germany (Kowalewski, 2015), Greece (Psaltopoulos and Balamou, 2005; Lampiris et al., 2018), Ireland (Morrissey and O'Donoghue, 2013; Morrissey, 2016), Northern Australia (Stoeckl, 2012), Scotland (Johns and Leat, 1987) and South Korea (Zhao and Choi, 2015; Flegg and Tohmo, 2016).

2.2.1. Location quotients

Following the generalised nomenclature, x_i^r and x^r are the total output of sector i in region r and the total output of region r respectively, while let x_i^n and x^n are the respective totals referred to at the national level. The simple location quotient (SLQ) for sector i in region r can be defined as:

$$SLQ_i = \frac{x_i^r/x^r}{x_i^n/x^n} \tag{1}$$

Or:

$$SLQ_i = \frac{x_i^r/x_i^n}{x^r/x^n} \tag{2}$$

Where the numerator presents the share of total national output of product i produced in region r and the denominator represents the share of total regional output in the national total.

The regional coefficient a_{ij}^r , which is the difference between the regional technical coefficient a_{ij}^r and the regional import coefficient a_{ij}^{sr} will be derived from the adjustment by the location quotient of the national coefficient a_{ij}^n for each industry. Thus:

Table 2
Irrigable areas and crop groups in the Region of Murcia. Source: Authors' compilation based on data from the Central Irrigation Union (CIU) and the Hydrographic Confederation of the Segura River (HCS).

	Total volume ¹ (m ³)					% River transfer	Area ² (ha)					Total
	River transfer	Desalinated water	Wells	Basin	Total		[1] Cereals and other extensive crops	[2] Horticulture	[3] Fresh fruits	[4] Citrus fruits	[5] Viticulture, olive grove and other crops	
Vega alta y media zone 1	4,530,269	290,165	181,299	0	5,001,733	90.6%	525	2,575	10,705	306	14,052	28,163
Vega alta y media zone 2	3,320,000	358,694	153,358	1,000,232	4,832,284	68.7%	0	213	2,186	865	587	3,851
Vega alta y media zone 3	2,757,232	34,148	398,479	4,739,471	7,929,329	34.8%	255	4,620	11,687	1,238	2,560	20,360
Vega alta y media zone 4	8,288,006	345,455	864,931	4,234,092	13,732,483	60.4%	137	1,986	600	5,785	355	8,863
Vega alta y media zone 5	3,315,531	81,797	298,920	62,713	3,758,960	88.2%	1,132	7,498	6,412	16,143	2,024	33,209
Campo de Cartagena	46,421,846	18,517,467	2,201,607	2,165,716	69,306,634	67.0%	104	27,488	1,594	12,863	1,023	43,072
Guadalentín valley sector 1	2,300,543	236,371	243,931	4,365,366	7,146,210	32.2%	63	455	51	414	107	1,090
Guadalentín valley sector 2	3,164,294	69,616	182,182	174,013	3,590,104	88.1%	130	3,208	141	715	141	4,335
Guadalentín valley sectors 3 and 4	4,150,141	104,097	181,471	2,203,329	6,639,038	62.5%	901	2,665	507	4,270	1,042	9,385
Guadalentín valley sectors 5 and 6	5,529,628	493,511	296,144	113,956	6,433,239	86.0%	249	3,904	83	5,502	644	10,382
Guadalentín valley sectors 7 and 8	10,399,462	1,567,244	474,376	2,803,010	15,244,092	68.2%	2,007	17,484	2,252	2,425	2,606	26,774
Mula and its region	2,702,184	110,000	333,827	383,931	3,529,941	76.6%	160	549	3,414	1062	1,185	6,370
Total	96,879,134	22,208,563	5,810,523	22,245,826	147,144,046	65.8%	5,663	72,645	39,632	51,588	26,326	195,854

¹Figures correspond to the average for 2018 and 2019.

²Estimate of the net area per ADU and type of product for 2013 by the Hydrological Planning Office of the CHS.

Table 3

Net irrigation demand by agricultural sector. *Source:* Authors' compilation based on data from the Hydrographic Confederation of the Segura River.

	m ³ /ha
[1] Cereals and other extensive crops	3,063
[2] Horticulture	4,826
[3] Fresh fruits	4,290
[4] Citrus fruits	5,110
[5] Vineyards, olive groves and other crops	1,530

Table 4

Estimated adjustment coefficients. *Source:* Authors' compilation based on data from the Regional Ministry of Agriculture, Livestock, Fisheries and Food of the Region of Murcia and the Hydrographic Confederation of the Segura River (HCS).

	Adjustment coefficient - irrigated production	Adjustment coefficient - for use
[1] Cereals and other extensive crops	13.3%	74.3%
[2] Horticulture	98.9%	70.5%
[3] Fresh fruits	33.4%	69.4%
[4] Citrus fruits	100.0%	76.6%
[5] Vineyards, olive groves and other crops	43.0%	79.4%

Table 5

Estimated values of agricultural production, gross value added and employment generated by irrigation water from the Tagus-Segura transfer in 2015. *Source:* Authors' compilation.

	Value of production (thousands of €)	Gross value added (thousands of €)	Employment (people)
[1] Cereals and other extensive crops	1,840	368	4
[2] Horticulture	615,940	331,431	21,463
[3] Fresh fruits	117,839	69,294	4,292
[4] Citrus fruits	337,272	198,796	12,313
[5] Vineyards, olive groves and other crops	2,817	1,547	73
Total agricultural crop branches	1,075,708	601,435	38,145

$$a_{ij}^{rr} = \begin{cases} (LQ_i^r) a_{ij}^n \text{ if } LQ_i^r < 1 \\ a_{ij}^n \text{ if } LQ_i^r \geq 1 \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

The simple location quotient (SLQ) considers the relative size of the supplying sector *i* and the regional size but does not take into account the relative size of the purchasing sector *j*, underestimating interregional trade and, therefore, import propensities.¹¹

A variant of the SLQ is the cross-industry location quotient (CILQ). This quotient seeks to make cell-by-cell adjustments rather than row-by-row adjustments to the matrix, considering the relative size of both the selling sectors, *i*, and the buying sectors, *j*, (Ramos, 1998). The CILQ is defined as:

$$CILQ_{ij} = \frac{x_i^r/x_i^n}{x_j^r/x_j^n} \quad (4)$$

Then:

$$a_{ij}^{rr} = \begin{cases} (CILQ_{ij}^r) a_{ij}^n \text{ if } CILQ_{ij}^r < 1 \\ a_{ij}^n \text{ if } CILQ_{ij}^r \geq 1 \end{cases} \text{ for } i \neq j, \\ a_{ij}^{rr} = \begin{cases} (SLQ_i^r) a_{ij}^n \text{ if } SLQ_i^r < 1 \\ a_{ij}^n \text{ if } SLQ_i^r \geq 1 \end{cases} \text{ for } i = j. \quad (5)$$

However, as can be seen, the inter-industry location quotient (IILQ) does not incorporate the relative size of the region, again underestimating inter-regional trade.

In an attempt to improve them, the Flegg location quotient, FLQ (Flegg and Webber, 1997) has been implemented:

$$FLQ_{ij}^r = \begin{cases} (\lambda) CILQ_{ij}^r \text{ if } i \neq j \\ (\lambda) SLQ_i^r \text{ if } i = j \end{cases},$$

where

$$\lambda = \left(\log_2 \left(1 + \frac{x^r}{x^n} \right) \right)^\delta, \quad 0 \leq \delta \leq 1. \quad (6)$$

Then:

$$a_{ij}^{rr} = \begin{cases} (FLQ_{ij}^r) a_{ij}^n \text{ if } FLQ_{ij}^r < 1 \\ a_{ij}^n \text{ if } FLQ_{ij}^r \geq 1 \end{cases}. \quad (7)$$

In order to properly capture the possible regional specialization that would lead a given region to be more specialised than indicated by the national coefficient, Flegg's (1997) methodological proposal was modified with a new proposal (Flegg and Webber, 2000), namely:

$$AFLQ_{ij}^r = \begin{cases} \left[\log_2(1 + LQ_j^r) \right] (FLQ_{ij}^r) \text{ if } LQ_j^r > 1 \\ FLQ_{ij}^r \text{ if } LQ_j^r \leq 1 \end{cases}. \quad (8)$$

And so:

$$a_{ij}^{rr} = \begin{cases} (AFLQ_{ij}^r) a_{ij}^n \text{ if } AFLQ_{ij}^r > 1 \\ (FLQ_{ij}^r) a_{ij}^n \text{ if } AFLQ_{ij}^r \leq 1 \end{cases}. \quad (9)$$

In practice, this augmented alternative does not generally perform better than its simple FLQ version (Bonfiglio, 2009), so it is still the FLQ alternative that continues to receive the most attention as the most suitable for undertaking regionalization processes.

As can be seen, the alternative proposed in the FLQ and AFLQ methodologies has a very significant dependence on the value given to the parameter δ (Flegg and Tohmo, 2019; Kowalewski, 2015; Lamonica and Chelli, 2018; Lampiris et al., 2019), the determination of which is highly costly and complex.

On the other hand, the two-dimensional location quotient, 2D-LQ, (Pereira-López et al., 2020, 2021) is based on the premise that the adjustment needed in the regionalisation process for the cost structure of a given industry does not necessarily have to be related to the adjustment needed in the sales structure, allowing a different adjustment parameter to be chosen for each of the two cases.

Finally, Fujimoto (2017,2019) establishes estimation alternatives that modify such procedures to obtain better estimates in the regionalisation process by improving cross-hauling estimation.

Fujimoto (2017) presents an alternative location quotient called DSLQ (Demand and Supply based Location Quotient) based on the need

¹¹ Round (1978) argued that a trade coefficient depends on four factors: the relative size of the supplying sectors "i", the relative size of the buying sectors "j", the relative regional size and regional specialization.

to statistically determine the regional production capacity in relation to the demand for each product between the nation and the region. This quotient has the expression:

$$DSLQ_i^R = \frac{X_i^R}{D_i^R} / \frac{X_i^N}{D_i^N}, \quad (10)$$

where the numerator represents the weight of the regional production of the product i over the regional demand for that product and the denominator gives the same proportion, but referring to the nation.

Using the methodology $DSLQ_i^R$ proposes a modification of the FLQ ratio (Fujimoto, 2019), using (estimated) value added as a weighting factor for regional size and substituting the ratio $CILQ_{ij}$ for his proposal (11). Its expression is:

$$FLQ_i^R = DSLQ_i^R \quad \text{where } \lambda = \left\{ \log_2 \left(1 + \frac{\sum_i V_i^R}{\sum_i V_i^N} \right) \right\}^\delta, \quad (11)$$

where V_i^R and V_i^N denote, respectively, value-added payments by sector i in the region R and the nation.

Therefore, this proposal modifies the quotient on which the smoothing is performed and cannot be considered an FLQ-type method (Flegg and Webber, 1997) or evaluated in terms of the accuracy of this quotient, as stated by Flegg et al. (2021). In this sense, in this work Fujimoto's proposal (DSLQ) has been considered as an alternative method to FLQ.

In Martínez-Alpañez et al. (2022), the superiority of Fujimoto's proposed method over the FLQ (Flegg, 2021) and 2D-LQ (Pereira-López et al., 2020) methods is demonstrated in a study of South Korea's 17 regions using the WAPE statistic. The proposed method yields more accurate estimates, with 70% of the estimated values differing by less than 1% from the optimal goodness-of-fit statistic, 3 regions showing differences between 1% and 3%, and only 2 regions exhibiting differences greater than 3%.

Furthermore, Fujimoto (2019) mathematically demonstrated that the DSLQ method overcomes both the aggregation bias and the underestimation of cross-hauling commonly associated with the LQ method.

2.2.2. The estimation of the unknown parameters in FLQ, 2DLQ and DSLQ methods

A crucial feature in the formulation of the FLQ, 2D-LQ and DSLQ methods is that they incorporate corrections (smoothing) on the estimated location quotient. Thus, the FLQ method (Eq. 6) incorporates a correction on the CILQ quotient as a function of the relative regional size and the parameter δ . It is precisely the determination of this parameter that has become one of the most controversial factors in the widespread application of FLQ as a regionalisation technique (Flegg and Tohmo, 2019; Kowalewski, 2015; Lamonica and Chelli, 2018; McCann and Dewhurst, 1998; Zhao and Choi, 2015) because the determinants for its estimation have not been definitively established.

In this work the DSLQ has been used, estimating the parameter δ by means of a novel proposal by the authors consisting of using the following regression:

$$\delta = \alpha_1 FTR + \alpha_2 FTS + \alpha_3 RS + e \quad (12)$$

where RS represents the regional size measured in terms of gross output, FTR corresponds to the weight of the transport flow of goods received for other regions and FTS corresponds to the weight of the transport flow of shipped goods for other regions (interregional transport) measured in tonnes over the total transport flow of goods, including both the

interregional transport flow and the transport flow generated within the region itself (intra-regional),¹² also measured in tonnes, and e is the residual.¹³

The determination of the parameter δ is critical, as it is directly related to the intensity of interregional trade. A higher δ value results in a lower regional coefficient, indicating a greater adjustment due to regional imports.

Buendía-Azorín et al. (2022, 2024) demonstrated the suitability of using interregional road freight traffic (IRFT) and imports from the rest of the world (IROW) as regressors in the estimation equations for the parameters associated with FLQ, 2D-LQ, and DSLQ. In this context, for δ , the regressors include the ratio of the region's propensity to import from the rest of the world relative to that of the nation, and the weight of road freight transport flows from other regions in the total freight transport flow. For the 2D-LQ parameters α and β , the regressors are regional size measured in terms of GDP and the weight of interregional freight transport flows in the total freight flow. Regarding the determination of the optimal δ , the minimization problem of the WAPE statistic is formulated and solved using the General Algebraic Modeling System (GAMS) software. This calculation yields improved results by obtaining a lower statistic value than those derived from minimizing the statistic over a set of δ values within the interval $[0,1]$ (typically 99 values in increments of 0.01).

2.2.3. Estimation of the inter-regional commerce

As it is generally known, a Bi-Regional Input-Output matrix includes both intra-regional and inter-regional submatrices. The previous section described the estimation method of the intra-regional submatrices, both for IOTRM and IOTROS; and this subsection discusses how to estimate the inter-regional submatrices.

The use of location quotients in regionalisation processes through inter-regional modelling has not been very widespread in the literature, though seen in Hermansson (2016) or Jahn (2017).

Thus, the procedure proposed by Jahn (2017) – which was tested for its goodness-of-fit in Jahn et al. (2020) but without comparing it with other methodologies – is based on the estimation of the domestic regional IOT using FLQ location quotients, thereby obtaining a first estimate of the regional IOT.

When estimating intra-regional trade using quotients, it makes sense to consider the generation of a residual resulting from the difference between the corresponding value of each element of the national IOT and the value obtained by applying the LQ methodology.

Let z_{ij} be the element of the national IOT purchased by the industry j from the industry i , and let \bar{z}_{ij}^r be the element ij estimated from the

¹² Statistics on road freight transport have been used, which are available from the Transport and Logistics Observatory in Spain, under the Ministry of Transport, Mobility, and Urban Agenda (<https://otle.transportes.gob.es/movilidad>). Specifically, the weight of inter-regional road freight transport flow, measured in tonnes, over the total freight transport flow—including both inter-regional transport flow and transport flow generated within the region itself (intra-regional)—also measured in tonnes, is utilized. Regarding imports from the rest of the world, data is available from the DataComex database, under the Ministry of Industry, Trade, and Tourism (<https://datacomex.comercio.es/>). The variable used is the share of imports from the rest of the world as a proportion of regional gross domestic product.

¹³ This regression was calculated for the regions of Korea, 2015, obtaining the values 0.311, 0.607 and 1.473 for coefficients, respectively, where the regressors are statistically significant at 1% with a $R^2 = 0.887$. The comparative study between the aforementioned methods undertaken by the authors for the homogeneous and uniform data for Korea from the multi-regional input-output table for the year 2015 (<https://ecos.bok.or.kr/>) confirms the superior accuracy of the DSLQ method. These results may be requested by contacting the authors.

domestic matrix of the region r , this residue can be defined as:¹⁴

$$e_{ij}^{FLQ} = z_{ij} - \sum_r z_{ij}^{sr} \geq 0. \tag{13}$$

Since the main focus of this paper is on the estimation of the input-output table for a particular region, an estimation of bi-regional trade between the region of interest and the “rest of the country” region is enough in order to establish the importance of the estimation of inter-regional trade. Thus, using a straightforward trade model (Jahn et al., 2020) and relative production data by industry (Flegg and Tohmo, 2019) – without the need to resort to gravity models for estimating inter-regional trade – the value of inter-regional trade between industries i, j and between regions r, s is established as follows:

$$h_{ij}^{sr} = \begin{cases} \bar{x}_i^s \bar{x}_j^r & \text{for } s \neq r \\ 0 & \text{for } s = r \end{cases}, \tag{14}$$

where \bar{x}_i^s is the (estimated) production of the industry i in the region s .

Scaling this result to ensure that the sum of h_{ij}^{sr} is equal to unity, the value of inter-regional trade can then be obtained by applying it to the residual:

$$z_{ij}^{sr} = \frac{h_{ij}^{sr}}{\sum_{r'} \sum_{s'} h_{ij}^{sr}} e_{ij}^{FLQ} = \frac{h_{ij}^{sr}}{\sum_{r'} \sum_{s'} h_{ij}^{sr}} \left(z_{ij} - \sum_r z_{ij}^{sr} \right) \text{ for } s \neq r. \tag{15}$$

At this point in the estimation process, the intra-regional trade matrix of internal transactions is already available, referring both to the specific region (in this study for the specific cases of the Region of Murcia) and to the so-called “rest of the country” region, as well as an estimate that includes the cross-industry transactions between these two regions, having to estimate the part corresponding to the final demand of both.

The procedure followed proposes the estimation of external trade branch by branch (or product by product) based on the weight of total exports, on the one hand, and imports, on the other, for the region of interest, and weighting this by the corresponding variable in the reference input-output table.

This regionalisation method, unlike the one presented by Canning and Wang (2004) on which it is based, offers an estimate of Total Final Demand (TFD), whose origin lies in each of the differentiated regions, regardless of the destination where consumption actually takes place. Thus, for example, household final consumption expenditure will not only include the value of such expenditure of residents of the region of interest, but will also include that of households of non-residents of the region who consume goods and services produced in the region.

2.2.4. Estimation of total final demand

To calculate the TFD, taking into account the typology of the table to be estimated – domestic – as well as the procedure proposed, and given the data that are normally available, there are grounds for proposing a subsequent alternative for its proper estimation, differentiating between domestic final demand and that which comes from the rest of the country. This is a decisive factor for being able to make estimates of the closed model from which the induced effects are derived in the event of final demand shocks.

The first estimate of the bi-regional table must be optimised by minimising the square of the distances, which is equivalent to maximising entropy, by solving the following optimisation problem (Jahn, 2017):

¹⁴ It must be noted that the graphs depicted in Pereira-López et al. (2022), which display the elements of the different matrices of the EA-19 territory and 4 of the countries in it, show that errors in the estimation mean that in some cases the sign of this residual may be negative.

$$\begin{aligned} MinS = & \sum_{i, j, s, r} \frac{(z_{ij}^{sr} - \bar{z}_{ij}^{sr})^2}{w_{ij}^{sr} z_{ij}^{sr}} + \sum_{i, r} \frac{(x_i^r - \bar{x}_i^r)^2}{x_i^r} + \sum_{i, r} \frac{(v_i^r - \bar{v}_i^r)^2}{v_i^r} \\ & + \sum_{i, r} \frac{(y_i^r - \bar{y}_i^r)^2}{y_i^r} + \sum_{i, r} \frac{(m_i^r - \bar{m}_i^r)^2}{m_i^r} + \sum_{i, r} \frac{(e_i^r - \bar{e}_i^r)^2}{e_i^r}. \end{aligned} \tag{16}$$

subject to:

$$\sum_{j, s} z_{ij}^{sr} + m_i^r + v_i^r = x_i^r. \tag{16.1}$$

$$\sum_{j, s} z_{ij}^{rs} + y_i^r + e_i^r = x_i^r. \tag{16.2}$$

$$\sum_{s, r} z_{ij}^{sr} = z_{ij}. \tag{16.3}$$

$$\sum_r x_i^r = x_i. \tag{16.4}$$

$$\sum_r v_i^r = v_i. \tag{16.5}$$

$$\sum_r y_i^r = y_i. \tag{16.6}$$

$$\sum_r m_i^r = m_i. \tag{16.7}$$

$$\sum_r e_i^r = e_i. \tag{16.8}$$

Where z_{ij}^{sr} is the value of intermediate inputs from sector i in region s to sector j in region r ; m_i^r is the imported inputs (from abroad); e_i^r is the exports (from abroad); v_i^r is value added; x_i^r is production; and y_i^r is the domestic final demand for the goods produced by sector i in region r . The corresponding variables without superscripts z_{ij} , m_i , e_i , v_i , x_i , y_i denote national aggregate values. And variables with an upper bar correspond to the respective initial estimates.

The imposed restrictions ensure, on the one hand, that the IO tables are consistent within each region and, on the other hand, that the regional values are consistent with the national aggregates. Thus, as far as the first question is concerned, constraints (16.1) and (16.2), respectively state that the sum of all types of input and the sum of all types of output are equal to the production of each sector in each region. As regards the second question, the constraint (16.3) ensures that the sum of the regional values of the intermediate inputs of sector i for sector j is equal to the corresponding national value. Furthermore, constraints (16.4) to (16.8) impose, respectively, that the sum of the regional values of regional production, gross added value, domestic final demand for the goods produced, imported inputs (from abroad) and exports (to outside the nation), must coincide, for each sector, with their respective national aggregate values.

In the same way, and bearing in mind that the main focus is on obtaining as accurate an estimate as possible of the intermediate inputs matrix, the above-mentioned expression can be simplified to ensure that the matrix is optimised. (Jahn et al., 2020). Such estimation is achieved by solving the following problem:

$$\begin{aligned} MinS = & \sum_{i, j, s, r} \frac{(z_{ij}^{sr} - \bar{z}_{ij}^{sr})^2}{w_{ij}^{sr} z_{ij}^{sr}} \text{ subject to:} \\ & \sum_i \sum_s z_{ij}^{sr} \leq x_j^r \\ & \sum_s \sum_r z_{ij}^{sr} = z_{ij}^r. \end{aligned} \tag{17}$$

The proof of the estimation accuracy of the procedure described in

Jahn (2017) is performed on the Korean multi-regional input-output table for the year 2005 (Jahn et al., 2020). This latter paper evaluates, when estimating inter-regional trade, the parameterisation of a different δ value for each region as opposed to the use of sectoral δ parameters, sectoral δ for each region or a single δ for all regions equally. Flegg and Tohmo (2019) argue that the alternative of using a sectoral parameter δ_j in each region (Kowalewski, 2015) gives optimal results for some regions, but not so good results for others, and they recommend the use of a different δ for each region.

With regard to inter-regional trade, while recognising that the use of gravity models offers optimal solutions, they conclude that the mere use of a simple trade model is adequate given the result obtained by the estimation. Considering that the final result of the process is expected to be a regionalised table of a single region, based on the estimation of the bi-regional table, this procedure was deemed to be the most appropriate.

3. Results and discussion

Based on the 2015 input-output table for Spain, the corresponding table for the Region of Murcia is estimated. The hybrid regionalisation procedure used stems from the estimation based on location quotients previously described, and by applying the DSLQ methodology, a table broken down to 51 productive branches is obtained. The outcome of applying this regionalisation procedure is used to assess the economic importance of irrigation water from the Tagus-Segura transfer in the Region of Murcia.

Fig. 1 summarises the estimated input-output matrix for the Region of Murcia. This Type B (non-competitive imports-type table) matrix provides a breakdown of sectoral purchases for each branch of activity, breaking down the total of imported purchases.

What is the economic impact in terms of production, gross added value and employment due to the irrigation water of the Tajo-Segura transfer if the current sectoral and water use structure is maintained? Conversely, what economic loss would occur in a hypothetical scenario assuming a 50% reduction in the volume of water that can be transferred for irrigation purposes? The following analysis aims to address these questions.

The breakdown of the total effect of agriculture associated with irrigation water from the Tagus-Segura transfer is conducted using production, income, and employment multipliers derived from the input-output demand model. This methodology enables the disaggregation of the total effect into direct, indirect, and induced impacts. The direct impact pertains to the generation of output and employment in activities that utilize water from the Tagus-Segura transfer for irrigation. The indirect impact reflects the output and employment generated through intermediate transactions between agricultural activities and the rest of the productive system. Finally, the induced impact captures

the generation of output and employment through expenditure made by workers in the different productive branches. For instance, to satisfy one euro of final demand, an additional 26 cents is generated through the interdependence between agriculture and other economic activities, which in turn leads to a further increase of 36 cents due to the spending driven by the rise in workers' incomes. Consequently, the total productive effort of the system amounts to 1.61 euros (the sum of direct, indirect, and induced impacts).

These results show the highest level of precision obtained using the most efficient methodological procedure (Martinez-Alpañez et al., 2022, 2023; Buendía-Azorín et al., 2024). A key innovation in the estimated regional table is the breakdown of the agricultural sector into five branches of plant production directly linked to water from the Tagus-Segura transfer. Therefore, the results of the study are more accurate and closely aligned with the regional reality, as they utilize the specific productive structure of the Region of Murcia. This contrasts with other studies that employ the national productive structure, which leads to greater bias in the estimates.

Although previous studies have not estimated the impact of the reduction in water transfers, the results of this work are in line with them in terms of the estimation of the macro-magnitudes of plant activities and their economic relevance. For example, Melgarejo and Martínez (2009) estimated that the production value of crops from irrigated areas of the transfer was 1,040 million euros. Similarly, Villar (2009) estimated a production value of 1,140 million euros.

Another study from 2015 (Hydrological Plan of the Segura River Basin 2015–2021) estimated, in 2012 euros, the production value at 2,987 million euros and 115,920 equivalent jobs. Other studies (PricewaterhouseCoopers, 2013 and 2020), using national input-output tables, estimated the agricultural sector's contribution to regional GDP at 1,286 million euros, supporting 73,610 jobs. These figures were later updated for 2019 in the transfer area, reporting a contribution to GDP of 1,516 million euros and 61,733 jobs.

Finally, in 2022, the PHDS 2022/2027 report estimated that the production value of the Segura River Basin amounted to 3,153 million euros (in 2019 euros), generating 118,690 equivalent jobs.

Fig. 2 shows the breakdown of the total effect of agriculture linked to irrigation water from the Tagus-Segura transfer. The contribution to the production system amounts to 1,741 million euros, which represents 2.9% of the total production of the Region of Murcia.

Disaggregating this cumulative effect, it can be observed that the agricultural activity associated with irrigation water in the Tagus-Segura transfer contributes to directly supporting 1,076 million euros (1.8%), indirectly supporting 275 million euros (0.46%) and inducingly supporting 390 million euros (0.65%) of the region's production.

The Gross Value Added contribution reached 801 million euros, which represents 3.1% of the total Gross Value Added of the Region of

Fig. 1. Input-output matrix Region of Murcia 2015. Type B symmetrical matrix (in thousands of euros). Source: Authors' compilation.

Fig. 2. Contribution to regional output, gross value added, and employment of agriculture associated with irrigation water from the Tagus-Segura transfer. Source: Authors' compilation.

Murcia, composed of a direct effect of 601 million euros (2.3%), an indirect effect of 108 million euros (0.42%) and an induced effect of 92 million euros (0.35%).

Lastly, agriculture linked to irrigation water in the Tagus-Segura transfer contributes to supporting 43,151 jobs, or 8.4% of total employment.

The results presented above, in relative terms, are consistent with those obtained by PricewaterhouseCoopers (2013), albeit with some notable differences. For instance, PricewaterhouseCoopers (2013) estimated that the contribution of agriculture in the transfer area accounted for 2.8% of the Gross Value Added, with the direct impact representing 30% of the agricultural Gross Value Added (compared to 3.1% and 40%, respectively, in this study). In terms of employment, they estimated a contribution of 6.2% of total employment, with a direct impact of 38.8% on employment in the agricultural sector (compared to 8.4% and 60%, respectively, in the present study). These disparities can be attributed to differences in the geographical area analyzed and, primarily, to variations in the input-output tables used.

Decisions are currently being taken by the authorities of the Spanish Ministry for Ecological Transition and Demographic Challenge to reduce the volume of water to be diverted from the Tagus River to the Segura: from the current monthly maximum of 38hm³ to 27 hm³. Furthermore, there is a high degree of uncertainty as to how the climate change impact on the environmental objectives in the Tagus River basin will be assessed and its repercussions on the volume of water that will be diverted according to the different uses of water – which include population supply, agricultural use, industrial use, and other uses (energy, recreational and environmental) – bearing in mind that urban supply is a priority by law.

When designing a possible real scenario, one must first consider that the regulation on the exploitation of the Tagus-Segura transfer is applied by the Central Commission for the Exploitation of the Tagus-Segura

Transfer, which is the body that authorises the water volumes to be transferred under normal hydrological conditions. Nevertheless, under exceptional hydrological circumstances, these are authorised by the Minister for Ecological Transition and Demographic Challenge, subject to a report from the Commission.

The current exploitation rule establishes that monthly levels are determined depending on the combined stocks in the Entrepeñas and Buendía reservoirs at the beginning of each month (Table 6), and the transfers are agreed in accordance with these levels, up to a combined annual maximum of 600hm³ for the Segura basin in each hydrological

Table 6
Exploitation rule definition.

Level	Conditions	Transferable volume (hm ³ /month)
1	Combined stocks in the Entrepeñas and Buendía reservoirs equal to or greater than 1,300hm ³ or combined inflows in the last twelve months equal to or greater than 1,200hm ³ .	60
2	Combined stocks in the Entrepeñas and Buendía reservoirs of less than 1,300hm ³ – without reaching the volume levels foreseen in Level 3 – and combined inflows in the last twelve months of less than 1,200hm ³ .	38 ^(*)
3	Combined stocks in Entrepeñas and Buendía do not exceed, at the beginning of the month, the values shown in Table 6 bis.	20
4	Combined stocks in Entrepeñas and Buendía of less than 400hm ³ .	0

(*) The Spanish Council of Ministers modified the level 2 exploitation rule at their meeting on 28/7/2021, reducing the maximum monthly water transfer from the current 38hm³ to 27hm³.

Source: Central Commission for the Exploitation of the Tagus-Segura Transfer (CCETST). Progress report. April 2020.

year.

This threshold of 400hm³ beyond which it can be considered that there is surplus water is established in the second final provision of Spanish Law 21/2015 (Spanish Official Gazette, 2015), which modifies the third additional provision of Law 10/2001 of the National Hydrological Plan, which set a threshold of 240hm³.

Table 6 bis

Combined stocks (in hm³) in the Entrepeñas and Buendía reservoirs defining the exceptional hydrological situations (Level 3).

Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep
613	609	605	602	597	591	586	645	673	688	661	631

Source: Central Commission for the Exploitation of the Tagus-Segura Transfer (CCETST). Progress report. April 2020.

Taking into account the foregoing assumptions, a *scenario of a 50% reduction in the volume of water transferred for irrigation* is envisaged. This scenario is based on the considerations included in the provisional outline of important issues of the Tagus River district for the third planning cycle 2021–2027. Thus, on the basis of different estimates of minimum flow thresholds, compatible with achieving the environmental objectives in the Tagus basin, the main hypothesis is an increase in the minimum flow from the current 6 m³/s to 8.5 m³/s in Aranjuez. This would imply a reduction in the volume of transferable water of 100hm³, i.e., 50% less than at present.¹⁵

Fig. 3 illustrates that the total impact of the 50% reduction of water transferred for irrigation on the production level of the regional economy amounts to –870 million euros, equivalent to 1.6% of the total regional production. The direct impact would reduce regional output by –538 million euros (–1.0%), the indirect impact, due to inter-industry consumption, by –137 million euros (–0.25%) and the induced impact, based on the income effect, by –194 million euros (–0.35%). When these figures are put in relation to the total agricultural production, the result is a 35% reduction.

In terms of Gross Value Added (GVA), the overall impact amounts to a decrease of €401 million, which represents 1.5% of the regional GVA in 2015. The direct impact accounts for –1.1%, the indirect impact for –0.22%, and the induced impact for –0.18%. Additionally, the loss in employment is estimated at 21,575 jobs, equivalent to 3.8% of total employment. Of this, 3.3 percentage points correspond to the direct impact, 0.3 percentage points to the indirect impact, and 0.2 percentage points to the induced impact.

On the other hand, if we focus on the total impact of the 50% reduction in water transferred for irrigation according to the different types of crops (Fig. 4), the relative loss (measured in percentage) in terms of production, gross added value stands out. and use of horticultural crops (–61.2%, –58.7% and –58%, respectively) and citrus crops (–28.2%, –30.1% and –30.8%, respectively).

4. Conclusions

In order to promote sustainable development, it is necessary to have appropriate methods and models that provide true, current and accurate information. Therefore, policy makers require a methodology to

¹⁵ Regarding the distribution of the transferred water, the fifth additional provision of Spanish Law 21/2015 establishes that the volumes authorised for transfer are to be distributed between supply and irrigation, 25% for the former and the remaining 75% for irrigation, up to the maximum of the annual allocations, and always ensuring at least 7.5hm³/month for urban supply. The maximum volume of water from the Tagus-Segura transfer devoted to urban supply is 110hm³ whereas the volume of water for irrigation is 400hm³. Nonetheless, in recent years the effective volume of water transferred for irrigation has averaged 200hm³.

quantify the effects of their decisions.

This study examines two central hypotheses regarding the importance of the Tagus-Segura water transfer for the Region of Murcia. The first hypothesis posits that irrigation water from the Tagus-Segura transfer is essential for sustaining regional agricultural output, gross value added (GVA), and employment. This hypothesis was confirmed through input-output (IO) analysis, which demonstrated the significant

economic contribution of the water transfer to the region.

The use of the input-output methodology enables the extraction of highly clear, precise and accurate results regarding the measurement of the economic relevance of any activity or the estimation of the economic impact generated by the occurrence of economic, social or environmental shocks. Thus, in order to analyse socio-economic and environmental impacts, it is essential to have an IO framework that adequately replicates the economy under study. Due to the lack of a regional matrix in the Region of Murcia, to carry out the analysis a Bi-Regional Input-Output matrix had to be built using a hybrid approach that combines a non-survey method based on Location Quotients and the well-known matrix balancing method RAS and the Jahn methodology (2017). Among the different regionalisation approaches based on location quotients, this paper has used the DSLQ approach, as the previous analyses undertaken by the authors show its superiority in estimation. The main issue for the use of this procedure lies in the estimation of the associated parameter, which becomes a crucial element in the regionalisation process. In this area, this work has provided an improvement in the implementation of the DSLQ method, incorporating as a novel contribution a proposal of estimation of this parameter. For such purpose, regressions are used whose independent variables are freight transport by road and the regional size.

Applying the estimation proposal has enabled us to obtain the input-output matrix for the Region of Murcia (Spain) and to estimate the total output contribution (direct, indirect, and induced), gross value added and employment in agriculture related to irrigation water from the Tagus-Segura transfer. The economic relevance of this infrastructure is significant, as it contributes to the generation and support of 2.9% of production, 3.1% of gross value added and 8.4% of employment in the Region of Murcia. Nevertheless, to truly reflect their real dimension, we must bear in mind that agricultural activities have important economic, social, and environmental implications, such as a prominent role in world trade, land management and the conservation and maintenance of natural.

The second hypothesis posits that a 50% reduction in the volume of transferable irrigation water would have a significantly negative impact on regional production, GVA, and employment. The bi-regional input-output (IO) model employed allows for precise quantification of the economic, social, and environmental impacts resulting from both the transfer itself and potential shocks, such as a reduction in transferable irrigation water. The results of a hypothetical 50% reduction in the transferable water for irrigation from the Tagus-Segura transfer – due to the new regulations on ecological flows to achieve the environmental objectives in the basin's water bodies – show a reduction in production of 870 million euros (1.6% of regional production), a reduction in Gross Value Added of almost 401 million euros (1.5% of regional gross value added) and a reduction in employment needs of 21,575 jobs (3.8% of regional employment).

In summary, the results of this study confirm the strategic importance of agriculture in the Region of Murcia. A 50% reduction in water from the Tagus-Segura Transfer would result in the closure of numerous

Fig. 3. Impacts of the 50% reduction of irrigation water from the Tagus-Segura transfer on production, gross value added and employment in the Region of Murcia. Source: Authors' compilation.

Fig. 4. Total impact of the 50% reduction in irrigation water from the Tajo-Segura transfer on production, gross added value and employment by type of crop in the Region of Murcia. Source: Authors' compilation.

agricultural operations dedicated to highly specialized vegetable crops with significant competitive capacity. This would have substantial negative repercussions on production, income, employment, export capacity, and Spain's trade balance. Additionally, it could hinder the critical digitalization and technological advancements currently underway in these operations, which have been producing highly positive and visible results in promoting more environmentally sustainable agriculture. The key recommendation for policymakers is that hydrological plans should integrate efficient, synergistic management strategies that balance the achievement of environmental objectives with the socio-economic development of different regions.

Although the analysis of potential mitigation strategies or alternative water sources that could offset the negative impacts resulting from reduced water transfer is beyond the scope of this study, we consider that the primary alternative is to replace the water received from the transfer with desalinated water. However, this alternative raises several key concerns: the first concerns the efficiency of desalinated water in terms of yield and cost across different types of production; the second pertains to the technical capacity to meet the reduction in transferred water; and the third addresses the environmental impact associated with the desalination of seawater.

Finally, it is worth highlight that, in the context of climate change, forecasts indicate a decrease in water resources, accompanied by an increase in the frequency and intensity of extreme events such as floods and droughts. These predictions would fully support the hypothesis regarding the reduction of water transfers from the Tajo-Segura system, thus reinforcing the findings presented in this study.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Conceptualization, Rubén Martínez Alpañez and José Daniel Buendía Azorín; methodology, Rubén Martínez Alpañez and José Daniel

Buendía Azorín; software, Rubén Martínez Alpañez; validation, Rubén Martínez Alpañez, José Daniel Buendía Azorín and, María del Mar Sánchez de la Vega; formal analysis, Rubén Martínez Alpañez, José Daniel Buendía Azorín, and María del Mar Sánchez de la Vega; investigation, Rubén Martínez Alpañez, José Daniel Buendía Azorín and María del Mar Sánchez de la Vega. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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